

Supplementary Figure 7 – Chromomap of Segmentally Duplicated Gene Clusters around *Schistosoma mansoni* subtelomeres. Gene clusters ($n < 2$) and single genes condensed into a single descriptor “Other SD Genes”. “Other Subtelomeric Genes” refers to subtelomeric genes that do not participate in segmental duplications. “No Gene” refers to the chromosomal region, with no annotated genes.